

GUAIACOL HYDRODEOXYGENATION OVER Ni₂P SUPPORTED ON 2D-ZEOLITES

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Abstract

Different 2D zeolites, namely lamellar ZSM-5 (L-ZSM-5), the corresponding silica pillared ZSM-5 (PI-ZSM-5) and an MCM-22 sample, were investigated as nickel phosphide supports and evaluated as catalysts for guaiacol hydrodeoxygenation (HDO). Characterization confirmed that all loaded materials preserved a high crystallinity degree with formation of the Ni₂P phase. The incorporation of Ni₂P reduced adsorption capacity, affecting differently the micro- or mesoporous systems, depending on the zeolitic support. Ni₂P deposition also modified the acidic properties of the zeolites due to the generation of new acid sites of moderate strength attributed to both Ni^{δ+} species (Lewis acid sites) and the presence of residual P-OH moieties (weak Brønsted acid sites). The catalysts were tested in the HDO of guaiacol at 220 and 260 °C and 40 bar of H₂. In all cases, ZSM-5 based catalysts exhibited higher conversions and HDO efficiencies than Ni₂P/MCM-22, which denotes that **MFI** zeolitic structure favors the deoxygenation of phenolic compounds, yielding cyclohexane as major reaction product. This excellent catalytic performance is attributed to the combination of high surface area and optimal acidic properties since a synergetic effect was achieved between the acid sites of the raw zeolitic support and those provided by nickel phosphide having an enhanced accessibility. Thus, the best HDO performance was obtained over Ni₂P supported on the pillared ZSM-5, showing a 78 % of guaiacol conversion and 95 % of selectivity towards deoxygenated compounds.

Keywords

Hydrodeoxygenation, 2D zeolites, nickel phosphides, guaiacol, bio-oil, acidity.

1. Introduction

The increasing energy demand, together with the environmental concerns derived from massive utilization of fossil fuels, has hastened the development of economical and sustainable energy resources. The conversion of lignocellulosic biomass into a liquid energy carrier (bio-oil), *via* fast pyrolysis, is among the most efficient and cost-effective options for the production of advanced biofuels. This transformation route presents high potential to reduce the greenhouse gas impact in the transportation sector. [1-3] However, pyrolysis bio-oils consist of a complex mixture of oxygenated organic compounds including phenolic derivatives, carboxylic acids, furans, aldehydes, ketones and esters, as well as a large amount of water and lignin oligomers. Consequently, they exhibit high viscosity, corrosiveness and relatively low heating value (LHV: 15-20 MJ/kg), which hinders their potential utilization in combustion engines and, hence, they must be subjected to an upgrading treatment to be used as advanced biofuels. [3,4]

Catalytic hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) has been extensively studied to remove oxygen from the organic fraction of pyrolysis bio-oils. HDO reactions are typically conducted under high hydrogen pressures (20-200 bar), moderate temperatures (200-300 °C) and using a heterogeneous catalyst. In this process, oxygen elimination to form water proceeds mainly by hydrogenolysis of C–O bonds or dehydration, but simultaneous hydrocracking reactions of large molecules also take place. [5,6]

In the last decade, transition metal phosphides, especially nickel phosphide, have attracted a great deal of attention as suitable HDO catalysts because of their effectiveness and stability in analogue hydrotreating processes (HDS and HDN) of petroleum feedstocks. [7,8] Interestingly, nickel phosphide has shown excellent catalytic performance in the HDO of model compounds such as phenol [9], guaiacol [10], anisole [11], cresols [12], dibenzofuran [13] as well as raw bio-oil. [14] Likewise, Ni-P based

catalysts present several advantages over more conventional active phases for hydrodeoxygenation. Thus, compared to traditional hydrotreating catalysts (NiMo and CoMo sulfides), they do not require the injection of an external source of sulfur. [13] In addition, they are cheaper than noble metal catalysts and promote less secondary reactions, such as hydrogenolysis of C–C bond and methanation, than transition metal catalysts. [12,15] The excellent catalytic behavior of Ni-P catalysts is related to the effect of P, which influences the electronic and geometrical properties of Ni atoms. [13,16] Consequently, nickel phosphide based catalysts exhibit, in addition to the metallic functionality, Lewis acid sites, attributed to $\text{Ni}^{\delta+}$ centers generated by electron transfer to P. Moreover, the usual presence of an excess of P on the catalyst surface results in the formation of P–OH groups (weak Brønsted sites), which promote dehydration and transalkylation reactions, leading to a higher deoxygenation degree compared to noble metal or transition metal based catalysts. [17] Likewise, these metal-free phosphorus species prevent catalyst deactivation, since they can interact effectively with water, avoiding the oxidation of the nickel phosphide nanoparticles. [13]

In order to improve the active sites accessibility, nickel phosphide has been usually supported on solids with high surface area, which affects to both active phase structure and dispersion. [11-16] Acid/basic properties of the support may influence the substrate activation and the HDO product distribution. [15] Hence, solids having different structure and acidity has been used as supports of nickel phosphide. Interesting results have been obtained over SiO_2 [13-16], ZrO_2 [18], TiO_2 [19], CeO_2 [15], alumina [18], mesostructured materials such as MCM-41 [20], SBA-15 [21], Al-SBA-15 [9], and ordered mesoporous carbons (CMK-3 and CMK-5) [9,22], as well as when using zeolites, including HY [15], HZSM-5 [14], HBeta [23] and, more recently, hierarchical ZSM-5 zeolite. [17] These latter works have proved that the utilization of zeolitic supports can

enhance the deoxygenation efficiency of Ni₂P, ascribed to the presence of strong acid sites in the zeolite surface, which promotes dehydration, hydrocracking and isomerization reactions, favoring the complete deoxygenation of phenolic derivatives. [17]

The present work investigates the utilization, as Ni-P supports, of different 2D zeolitic materials, namely lamellar ZSM-5, the corresponding pillared ZSM-5 (a derivative of lamellar ZSM-5) and MCM-22 with platelet-like crystal morphology. These materials are characterized by having a high proportion of external/mesopore surface compared to the conventional zeolites. [24] The high external surface can provide a better dispersion of the active phase and reduce the diffusional and steric restrictions in comparison with the conventional 3D zeolites, favoring the processing of the bulky molecules typically present in bio-oils. [25] The catalytic performance of the final bifunctional systems was tested in guaiacol hydrodeoxygenation. This is a suitable model reaction because the reactant contains both methoxy and hydroxyl groups being characteristic functionalities of lignin derivatives.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Catalysts preparation

2.1.1. Synthesis of lamellar and pillared ZSM-5 zeolites

The synthesis of the lamellar ZSM-5 (*L-ZSM-5*) was performed following the procedure described by Choi et al. [26] Thereby, 5.91 g of Al₂(SO₄)₃·16 H₂O (Fluka) were added over a 0.001 M NaOH (Penta, Czech Republic) solution. Once the aluminum source was dissolved, 6.47 g of sulphuric acid (Penta, Czech Republic) and 86 g of tetraethylortosilicate (TEOS, Aldrich) were mixed with the previous solution. The mixture was stirred for 70 min to hydrolyze the TEOS. Subsequently, 30 g of the structure directing agent (SDA) (C₂₂H₄₅-N⁺(CH₃)₂-C₆H₁₂-N⁺(CH₃)₂-C₆H₁₃ Br₂, in short C₂₂₋₆₋₆Br₂), prepared following the Na et al. recipe [27,28], were incorporated to the prior solution.

The mixture so obtained was homogenized for 30 min. Finally, 35 g of water were added to compensate the weight loss caused by evaporation of ethanol formed by TEOS hydrolysis. The Si/Al molar ratio of the synthesis gel was 22. The hydrothermal crystallization proceeded in a 1 l stainless steel Parr autoclave at 155 °C under autogenous pressure and stirring (350 rpm) for 144 h. The solid product was recovered by filtration, washed with distilled water, dried overnight at 65 °C and calcined in air at 540 °C for 8 h under static conditions. After that, the calcined zeolite was ion-exchanged into the NH₄⁺ form by four repeated treatments with 1.0 M NH₄NO₃ solution for 4 h at room temperature (100 ml of solution/1 g of zeolite). Finally, the sample was calcined at 450 °C for 90 min under static air conditions to convert it into the protonic form.

The lamellar ZSM-5 zeolite obtained in the above synthesis was pillared following the general procedure described elsewhere [29], using TEOS as pillaring agent. Thus, 190 ml of TEOS (Aldrich) were mixed with 18.8 g of as-synthesized dry L-ZSM-5 and stirred at 85 °C for 20 h. Subsequently, the solid material was collected by centrifugation and dried at room temperature for 36 h. The resultant material was mixed with 2000 ml of distilled water and 50 ml of ethanol and stirred for 24 h at room temperature to promote the TEOS hydrolysis. Finally, the solid was filtered, dried overnight at 65 °C and calcined in air at 540 °C for 6 h under static conditions. The calcined sample was converted into the protonic form, as described above for L-ZSM-5. The resulting material was denoted as *PI-ZSM-5*.

2.1.2. Synthesis of MCM-22 zeolite

The synthesis of MCM-22 zeolite was carried out according to the procedure described by Chlubná et al. [30] Firstly, 2.4 ml of NaOH and the proper amount of NaAlO₂ (Riedel-de-Haen, [Si/Al]_{MOL} = 40) were dissolved in 200 g of distilled water. Then, 116.2 g of silica (LUDOX AS-30) and 22 ml of hexamethyleneimine were added

and vigorously stirred for 30 min. After that, the hydrothermal treatment was carried out in a stainless-steel reactor placed horizontally in an oven on rollers (40 rpm) at 150 °C for 96 h. Then, the solid products were recovered by centrifugation, washed several times with distilled water and dried overnight at 110 °C. The resultant material was finally calcined under inert atmosphere for 3 h at 480 °C and, subsequently, in air for 8 h at 540 °C under static air conditions. The calcined sample was ion-exchanged into the NH_4^+ form, as described above for L-ZSM-5, and calcined under static air conditions at 480 °C for 6 h to convert it into the protonic form.

2.1.3. Nickel phosphide incorporation

The supported metal phosphide catalysts were obtained by means of impregnation of the zeolitic supports with the active phase precursors ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Aldrich) and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (Aldrich)) followed by a Temperature Programmed Reduction (TPR) method published elsewhere. [8] A Ni/P molar ratio of 1.0 was used because, according to previous reports [13,21], this favors the formation of the Ni_2P metal-rich phase with a total nickel loading of 10 wt%. The loaded materials were first dried at room temperature overnight, then at 120 °C for 24 h and subsequently calcined at 500 °C for 4 h under static air conditions. After that, the phosphate catalysts so-obtained were pelletized, crushed and sieved with 40-60 mesh (250-180 μm). The pelletized samples were reduced under H_2 flow (80 ml/min) in a tubular furnace at 650 °C during 3 h. Immediately after the reduction step, the catalysts were passivated by progressive introduction of an air flow at room temperature. The passivation treatment was used to create an oxide layer to avoid the re-oxidation by contact with the air during the transfer to the reactor.

2.2. Catalyst characterization

The structure and crystallinity of parent zeolites and loaded catalysts was determined by X-ray powder diffraction on a Philips Diffractometer (model PW 2040/00

X'Pert MPD/MRD using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm). Aluminum, nickel and phosphorous contents of each sample were measured by ICP-OES on a Perkin Elmer Optima 7300 DV instrument. Transmission electron micrographs (TEM) were recorded using a TECNAI 20 Philips operating at 200 kV. Prior to the analysis, the powder sample was ultrasonically dispersed in acetone and then deposited on a carbon film supported on a copper grid. Particle size distribution was determined from the images taken using Image J software.

Argon gas adsorption-desorption isotherms at -186 °C were recorded using a Quantachrome AUTOSORB iQ volumetric analyzer equipped with 1 Torr transducer. Surface areas were determined using the BET equation. Pore size distributions as well as surface and volume corresponding to both micro- and mesoporous systems were calculated using NL-DFT model to the adsorption branch of the isotherms. The overall acidity of the parent and loaded materials was measured by ammonia temperature programmed desorption (NH₃-TPD) in a Micromeritics AUTOCHEM 2910 apparatus. Previously to the analyses, the samples were outgassed under a He flow at 600 °C during 60 minutes. After cooling to 100 °C, a 10 vol % He/NH₃ mixture was passed through the sample for 90 min. The physisorbed ammonia was removed by flowing He at 100 °C for 30 min. The chemically adsorbed ammonia was determined by increasing the temperature up to 550 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The ammonia concentration in the effluent stream was monitored using a TCD detector.

Solid-state ²⁷Al nuclear magnetic resonance (MAS NMR) of the powder samples was performed on a Varian Infinity 400 MHz spectrometer fitted with a 9.4 T magnetic field and using 4 mm ZrO₂ rotors. The measurements were carried out at room temperature, spinning the sample at 12 kHz with a pulse width of 1 s.

The concentration of Lewis (C_{LEWIS}) and Brønsted ($C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$) acid sites was determined after adsorption of pyridine (Py) followed by FTIR analysis using a Nicolet 6700 spectrometer with a transmission MTC/A detector. Zeolites were pressed into self-supporting wafers with a density of $\sim 10 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$ and activated *in situ* at $450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and vacuum ($5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Torr) for 4 h. Pyridine adsorption was carried out at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 min at a partial pressure of 3.5 Torr. All spectra were recorded with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} by collecting 128 scans for a single spectrum at room temperature. Spectra were recalculated using a wafer density of 10 mg cm^{-2} . Concentration of Lewis and Brønsted acid sites were evaluated from the integral intensities of bands at 1454 cm^{-1} (C_{LEWIS}) and at 1545 cm^{-1} ($C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$) using the corresponding extinction coefficients: $\epsilon(\text{Lewis}) = 2.22 \text{ cm } \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$, and $\epsilon(\text{Brønsted}) = 1.67 \text{ cm } \mu\text{mol}^{-1}$. [31,32]

Finally, the TPR profiles were obtained in a Micromeritics AUTOCHEM 2910 apparatus by passing a 10 vol % H_2/Ar flow (50 ml/min) through the sample while heating from room temperature to $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The hydrogen consumption was recorded using a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). A cooling trap (liquid N_2 and isopropanol) placed between the sample and the TCD was used to retain the water produced during the reduction test.

2.3. Catalytic activity

The HDO catalytic tests were carried out in a 100 ml stainless steel (SS) high-pressure stirred batch reactor using guaiacol as phenolic model compound. For each run, a mixture of 1.5 g of guaiacol (Aldrich), 50 ml of decalin (Aldrich) and 150 mg of passivated catalyst were loaded into the reactor. After that, the autoclave was purged twice with N_2 and then pressurized to 40 bar of H_2 . Then, the reaction system was heated to the reaction temperature (220 and $260 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) under vigorous stirring (1000 rpm). After the reaction time (2 h), the reactor was rapidly cooled down using a water and ice mixture.

Gaseous products were collected in a sampling bag and subsequently analyzed in a dual channel Agilent CP-4900 Micro Gas Chromatograph equipped with a TCD.

The quantitative analysis of liquid products was performed by using a gas chromatograph Agilent 7890 A equipped with a FID and a HP-INNOWAX column. The catalyst performance was assessed from the values of the guaiacol conversion, X_{GUA} (%), Turnover frequency (TOF) and both hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) and hydrodearomatization (HDA) efficiencies. In addition, the product distribution was evaluated in terms of selectivity, S_i (%). These catalytic activity parameters were calculated according the following formulas:

$$X_{GUA} (\%) = \left(1 - \frac{n}{n_0}\right) \times 100 \quad [1]$$

$$HDO (\%) = \left(\frac{n_0 \times X_{GUA} - \sum n_i b_i}{n_0 \times X_{GUA}}\right) \times 100 \quad [3]$$

$$HDA (\%) = \left(\frac{n_0 \times X_{GUA} - \sum n_i c_i}{n_0 \times X_{GUA}}\right) \times 100 \quad [4]$$

$$S_i (\%) = \left(\frac{n_i}{n_0 - n}\right) \times 100 \quad [5]$$

Where n_0 and n are the initial and final moles of guaiacol in the mixture, respectively, n_i represent the moles of product i in the final mixture, b_i is the number of oxygen atoms per product i and c_i is the number of aromatic rings per molecule of product i .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalysts characterization

Three different 2D zeolites: a lamellar ZSM-5 zeolite (L-ZSM-5), the corresponding pillared material (PI-ZSM-5), and a platelet-like MCM-22 sample, have been synthesized in this work and evaluated as supports of nickel phosphide. Their physicochemical properties were compared and HDO catalytic activity of these bifunctional catalysts was tested.

First, phase composition and crystallinity of the Ni₂P loaded samples were studied by wide-angle XRD analyses (Fig. 1.A and B). Both ZSM-5 raw zeolites show diffraction lines in 2 θ ranges of 8–10° and 20–25°, which correspond to the **MFI** structure, whereas the pattern recorded for MCM-22 sample displays the typical reflections of the **MWW** topology, appearing particularly in the 5–10° 2 θ range.

Relatively low intensity and broadening of the lines in XRD patterns of the 2D zeolites are due to a reduced crystal thickness (to a unit cell level) of the zeolitic nanosheets, as it is evidenced in the TEM images corresponding to the zeolitic supports (Fig. 2 a, c, e). These signals remain almost unmodified in the XRD spectra corresponding to the loaded catalysts denoting that both zeolitic structures are preserved after nickel phosphide incorporation. [28,30] In addition, XRD patterns of the supported catalysts exhibit reflections at 2 θ (°) = 40.7, 44.6 and 47.4, corresponding to the metal-rich nickel phosphide phase (Ni₂P). The absence of diffraction signals corresponding to metallic Ni suggests the complete conversion of Ni into Ni₂P. The formation of this phosphide phase is favored by the utilization of an excess of phosphorus during the impregnation process ([Ni/P]_{MOL} ~ 1.0). [33]

Both L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5 supports and the corresponding loaded materials were further analyzed by low angle XRD (SI Fig. 1). In the case of the lamellar sample, a weak diffraction signal is detected at 2 θ values 1.4°, which suggests the presence of some interlamellar structural correlation. In the case of the PI-ZSM-5 support, the sharp reflection observed at 2 θ values of 1.6° reveals the existence of some mesostructured order due to the uniform arrangement of the zeolite layers supported by the silica pillars. These multilamellar assemblies can be also observed in the TEM images presented in Fig. 2 (b and c). However, after the Ni₂P active phase loading, these signals weaken considerably for both materials, which can be assigned to a partial loss of the

multilamellar assembly, as can be seen in the TEM images (Fig. 2.b and d). TEM micrographs of all supported catalysts confirm a high density of rounded Ni₂P particles, with diameters ranging from 5 to more than 30 nm. This heterogeneous size distribution (SI Fig. 2) can be related to the high nominal metallic load used (10 wt% of nickel). [17] Nevertheless, the differences in the mean crystallite diameter between samples are relatively small, being comprised between 9.8 to 10.5 nm (see Table 1). These Ni₂P nanoparticles exhibit spherical morphology in all samples, although for the material Ni₂P/PI-ZSM-5, there is a significant amount of nanoparticles with elongated shape (Fig. 2.c and d). This fact can be a consequence of the steric constraints imposed by the pillared structure.

Table 1 summarizes the chemical compositions, determined by ICP-OES analysis, of the loaded catalysts. The estimated Si/Al molar ratios are comprised between 31 and 49 (1.37 and 0.9 wt% Al, respectively). As expected for pillared support, the Si/Al molar ratio is higher than that corresponding to the lamellar zeolite because of the additional silica incorporated during the pillaring treatment. For supported catalysts, nickel content is very similar and is quite close to the nominal load (10 wt%). Interestingly, these samples show Ni/P molar ratios ranged from 1.21 to 1.49, which are higher than the molar proportion used during the support impregnation ($[\text{Ni}/\text{P}]_{\text{MOL}}=1$), but lower than the stoichiometric ratio of the metal rich Ni₂P active phase. These results indicate that, although some quantity of volatile phosphorous was released during the reduction treatment, a considerable amount of unreacted phosphorus species remains over the catalysts surface, presumably leading to the formation of P-OH groups, as it has been previously found for other Ni₂P catalysts. [34]

Ar adsorption-desorption isotherms measured at -186 °C and pore size distributions calculated using NL-DFT method are given in Fig. 3. For the zeolitic

supports, the isotherms (Fig. 3. A-C) show combined characteristics of type I and IV isotherms, according to the IUPAC classification, because of the bimodal pore architecture of these samples. The Ar uptake observed at low relative pressures is characteristic of microporous solids, whereas the progressive adsorption observed at medium-high relative pressures is related to the presence of a secondary porous system. In the case of MCM-22, this adsorption mainly occurs at relative pressures higher than 0.8 and can be assigned to the filling of the interparticular voids. Consequently, non-uniform pores with sizes higher than 20 nm can be observed in the corresponding pore size distribution (Fig. 3.F).

L-ZSM-5 zeolite displays a significant adsorption capacity at intermediate relative pressures ascribed to the existence of interlamellar voids arising from the irregular array of the zeolitic layers (Fig. 3.D). Likewise, the isotherm of L-ZSM-5 exhibits an H3 hysteresis loop, which is often observed when non-polar gases are adsorbed over aggregates of small slit shaped pores. [35] The isotherm belonging to the material PI-ZSM-5 displays a clear inflection point at $P/P_0 = 0.4$, which denotes the existence of a uniform mesoporosity, typically observed in pillared zeolites. [30] This mesoporous system exhibits a narrow PSD centered at 3.5 nm (Fig. 3.E), which corresponds to the interlayer spacing produced by the pillaring procedure.

In all cases, the isotherm shape is preserved after nickel phosphide deposition, suggesting that no substantial changes occur in the porous structure. In the case of both ZSM-5 based samples, this observation confirms that the interlayer assembly of Ni₂P/L-ZSM-5 and Ni₂P/PI-ZSM-5 catalysts is mainly preserved after metal phosphide deposition, in spite of the reduction of the diffraction signal observed in low angle XRD analyses. Nevertheless, the active phase loading reduces the Ar adsorption capacity due to the surface coverage and partial pore blocking caused by Ni₂P nanoparticles. As

expected, the values of the main textural parameters (estimated regarding the mass of the parent support) are also lowered (Table 2). Depending on the parent zeolite, Ni₂P incorporation affects differently the textural parameters ascribed to each microporous and mesoporous networks. Thus, for L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5 zeolites, the decrease in the textural properties is higher for the additional porous system, indicating that most of the Ni₂P nanoparticles are placed in the mesoporous channels, interlamellar voids or deposited on the external surface of the zeolitic layers. In the case of MCM-22, the more perceptible decrease occurs in both surface and volume assigned to the microporous system, which can be assigned to the micropore blockage produced by the metallic nanoparticles formation inside the large cavities (18.2 x 7.1 Å) accessible via 12-membered windows, typical of the MWW structure.

²⁷Al MAS NMR spectra allow envisaging the state and coordination of Al species as well as their stability during the impregnation treatment (Fig. 4). All zeolites exhibit an intense peak at about 54 ppm, typically assigned to tetrahedral Al atoms incorporated into the zeolite framework (Al_F). [36,37] In the case of MCM-22 zeolite (Fig. 4.A), this signal is wider due to the overlapping of two peaks at 55 ppm (FAI₁) and 48 ppm (FAI₂), indicating the presence of two crystallographically different framework Al sites. According to the literature, the chemical shift at 55 ppm is assigned to Al species located inside the micropores (T1, T3, T4 and T8 sites) while the resonance at 48 ppm is related with Al species placed at the external surface and/or the large cavities of the **MWW** framework (T6 and T7 sites). [38,39] A second signal, located at about 0 ppm, is attributed to extraframework aluminum species with octahedral coordination (EFAI). This resonance is quite sharp and intense in the case of MCM-22 zeolite, being rather smaller for both 2D ZSM-5 samples (Fig. 4. B and C). Upon nickel phosphide loading, the signal of extraframework aluminium turns lower and broader and is slightly displaced

towards lower chemical shifts. This effect can be assigned to distortion of the environment of these AlO_6 octahedra due to the formation of a small proportion of aluminophosphates as a consequence of the reaction of phosphorus precursors and the EFAl species. [40] Interestingly, the resonance corresponding to tetrahedral Al atoms remains almost unmodified for the loaded zeolites. This denotes the high stability of the framework Al species during the impregnation and reduction thermal treatment, but also indicate that these centers are not very affected by the presence of Ni_2P , which preferentially placed in the external surface.

This statement is confirmed by the calculation of the full-width-at-half-maximum values (FWHM) for the signal assigned to the tetrahedral Al atoms, which provides a measurement of the uniformity of the Al environment. In the case of both ZSM-5 samples, the FWHM values are quite similar before and after the impregnation-reduction treatment, which can be related with the fact that the majority of the Ni_2P nanoparticles are allocated in the mesoporous and the external surface of the zeolite, having a low impact in the environment of Al atoms present inside the zeolitic micropores. However, for MCM-22, the FWHM value increases in a greater extension after the metal loading, which can be a consequence of the presence of a high amount of Ni_2P nanoparticles inside of the **MWW** cavities.

Adsorption of pyridine was used to evaluate the nature and strength of the acid sites of the zeolitic supports. Fig. 5.A. illustrates the infrared spectra after adsorption/desorption of pyridine collected at 150 °C. For all samples, it is possible to distinguish three absorption bands. Firstly, the well-defined and intense signal at 1490 cm^{-1} is traditionally ascribed to pyridine adsorbed on both Lewis (LAS) sites and Brønsted acid sites (BAS). The absorption band at 1545 cm^{-1} is assigned to pyridinium ions (PyH^+) produced by the pyridine chemisorption on Brønsted acid centers (BAS), while the signal

located at 1456 cm^{-1} is related to pyridine molecules strongly adsorbed on Lewis acid sites, (LAS). Moreover, in the spectra corresponding to the MCM-22 and L-ZSM-5 zeolites, an additional signal at 1442 cm^{-1} is detected, which can be assigned to Py species interacting with weak LAS or weakly acidic silanols groups, whose intensity depends on their relative concentration in the sample. Accordingly, this band is not observed in the spectrum of the PI-ZSM-5 zeolite, which exhibits a lower Al content.

The concentrations of BAS and LAS were calculated from corresponding integrated areas (Fig. 5.B) using the extinction coefficients reported in the literature. [31,32]. MCM-22 exhibits higher BAS concentration than L-ZSM-5 zeolite, although the latter sample shows higher Al content. An opposite trend was observed for the LAS concentration. Nevertheless, the overall acidity values ($C_{\text{BAS}} + C_{\text{LAS}}$) are quite similar for both materials. In the case of the PI-ZSM-5 zeolite, both BAS and LAS concentrations are quite lower than in the previous samples, which can be assigned to the introduction of an additional amount of amorphous silica during the pillaring treatment.

For further investigation of the acidic properties of catalysts before and after Ni_2P deposition, both parent and the loaded materials were subjected to NH_3 -TPD analyses. The resultant desorption profiles are depicted in Fig. 6. For L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5, a clear maximum centered at $190\text{--}210\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is observed, which can be assigned to the presence of acid sites with low-moderate strength. These peaks exhibit a shoulder around $300\text{--}400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which denotes the presence of strong acid sites, which probably correspond with those located inside the zeolitic **MFI** micropores. However, due to the layered structure of both samples, the contribution of this acid site is attenuated. MCM-22 zeolite exhibits a bimodal acid sites distribution, with two maximums centered at $170\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $320\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The last maximum can be associated with the acid sites located inside the zeolitic micropores of the **MWW** topology, including both located in the 10 MR and 12

MR supercages. This peak is clearer in this material because of the higher thickness of the MWW sheets in comparison with the MFI layers. In addition, for these samples, the amount of desorbed NH_3 at temperatures $> 350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is lower than that obtained over MCM-22, which can be associated to the higher proportion of microporous surface in the latter material, in which usually are located the strongest acid sites. The overall acidity values were comprised in the range 0.15–0.19 mmol NH_3/g , being higher for MCM-22 and L-ZSM-5 because of higher Al content.

The TPD profiles were significantly modified after Ni_2P incorporation. Thus, the maximum NH_3 desorption peak located at low temperatures (170–210 $^\circ\text{C}$) increases considerably and becomes wider, achieving temperatures around 450 $^\circ\text{C}$, which denotes the generation of a new acidity with moderate strength. According to the literature, these new acid sites arise from the overlapped contribution of both Brønsted and Lewis acid sites, ascribed, respectively, to the P–OH groups and to the electron-deficient Ni sites ($\text{Ni}^{\delta+}$). [9,13,17,41,42] Several authors assigned the presence of the P–OH groups to a signal registered around 200 $^\circ\text{C}$ while the desorption at 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ is related to $\text{Ni}^{\delta+}$ Lewis acid sites [42,43]. The generation of this new acidity is more noticeable for both ZSM-5 zeolites, which could imply that the availability of larger surface areas allows the formation of more P–OH species and $\text{Ni}^{\delta+}$ Lewis acid sites on the catalyst surface. As a result, the overall concentration of acidic sites, as displayed in Fig. 7, are significantly increased after the metal loading, especially in the case of the PI-ZSM-5 zeolite, in which the amount of the desorbed NH_3 is more than double that their initial acidity value. Likewise, in the case of the catalyst based on the MCM-22 zeolite, the NH_3 desorption at high temperatures diminishes, suggesting a reduction of the concentration of the strongest acid sites as a consequence of the interaction with Ni_2P nanoparticles, which are preferentially deposited in the micropores.

H₂-TPR analyses were carried out to evaluate the reduction behavior of the nickel phosphide precursors over the different zeolitic supports. In the TPR curves (SI Fig. 3), no obvious reduction peaks were observed at temperatures lower than 500 °C, denoting the absence of NiO species. Likewise, a broad H₂ consumption signal, ranged from 500 to 900 °C, appears in the reduction profiles of the three zeolitic supports, which is typically assigned to the reduction of nickel phosphate or oxyphosphate to nickel phosphide phases. [12,44] However, some differences can be observed depending on the zeolitic support. In the case of the 2D ZSM-5 samples, a clear shoulder appears around 665 °C, which can be associated to the reduction of Ni₂P precursors with lower interaction with the support as could be those present in the mesoporous and external surface, whose contribution is higher in these samples. In addition, the maximum reduction temperature is shifted towards higher values (from ~740 °C in the MCM-22 to ~760 °C for ZSM-5 samples), which can denote a higher interaction between nickel phosphide precursors present within **MFI** zeolitic micropores because of its smaller size.

3.2. Catalytic activity

The catalytic activity of the Ni₂P-zeolitic catalysts was tested in hydrodeoxygenation of guaiacol under a H₂ pressure of 40 bars using two different temperatures: 220 °C and 260 °C. It should be noticed that the molar balance of the identified products was closed at 95–100 % in all the catalytic experiments.

Fig. 7 depicts guaiacol conversions together with both hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) and hydrodearomatization (HDA) efficiencies. At 220 °C, all Ni₂P catalysts show a moderate catalytic activity in guaiacol HDO. Thus, both 2D ZSM-5 based samples exhibit similar conversion values, being close to ~30 %, whereas Ni₂P/MCM-22 has lower activity (with a conversion of 19.4 %), denoting the significant effect of the zeolitic

support on the activity. These results can be related to two factors. Firstly, both **MFI** zeolites preserve much better the micropore surface area after the Ni₂P loading since most of the Ni₂P nanoparticles are allocated in the external and/or mesoporous surface, being more accessible to the organic substrate. Likewise, according to the NH₃ desorption profiles, the contribution of the acidity assigned to the Ni₂P (which is related to a high density of P–OH as well as Ni^{δ+} Lewis acid sites) is more noticeable in these materials than in MCM-22.

The influence of the zeolitic support is also evidenced by the values of HDO and HDA yields estimated for each catalyst. Thus, at 220 °C, both **MFI** zeolites display quite high HDO and HDA yields with values around 95 % while, for MCM-22 loaded catalyst, these values decrease to 56.6 and 73.5 %, respectively. In addition, for the MCM-22 catalyst, HDA efficiency is almost 25 % higher than the HDO degree. These results indicate that the ZSM-5 based catalysts favor the complete hydrodeoxygenation of phenolic compounds in comparison with the Ni₂P/MCM-22 sample. As it expected, in the experiments carried out at 260 °C, the conversion substantially increases, achieving values of ~ 71, 78 and 61 % for Ni₂P/L-ZSM-5, Ni₂P/PI-ZSM-5 and Ni₂P/MCM-22, respectively. These results confirm that **MFI** zeolites exhibit better HDO catalytic behavior. Likewise, the HDO degree remains close to 95 % for **MFI** based materials, while increased to 88 % over the Ni₂P/MCM-22 sample at this higher operation temperature.

The product selectivity is shown in Fig. 8. Because of the large number of chemicals present in the liquid phase (many of them at rather low concentration), the selectivity percentages group compounds of the same family together. For the **MFI** samples, independently of the reaction temperature used, the main reaction product was cyclohexane, with selectivity exceeding 80 %. This is an outstanding result, considering

that cyclohexane is one of the main components of gasoline with a high octane number (~83). [45] Other aliphatic hydrocarbons such as methylcyclopentane and n-hexane are also detected, due to the occurrence of isomerization and ring opening reactions catalyzed by acid sites. The selectivity to these compounds increases slightly with the reaction temperature (~6.3 % vs. 9 %). Oxygenated aromatics, such as anisole and phenol, as well as oxygenated aliphatic compounds, mainly methoxycyclohexane, were also detected in low proportions (<5%). In the case of Ni₂P/MCM-22, the selectivity towards cyclohexane is lower, showing values of ~ 39 and 65 % at 220 °C and 260 °C, respectively, due to the presence of a higher fraction of oxygenated compounds in comparison with MFI-based materials. This fact can be attributed to a lower contribution of the acidity generated after the nickel phosphide loading, as it is evidenced by the NH₃ TPD analyses. In addition, the preferential formation of the Ni₂P nanoparticles in the MWW cavities, as suggested by the changes in textural properties upon metal deposition, could difficult the interaction between the phenolic substrate and the active sites, leading to worse catalytic behavior than the ZSM-5 based catalysts. At 220 °C, methylcyclohexanediol and anisole are the main oxygenated products, with selectivity 27.7 % and 19.4 %, respectively. Anisole is produced as a result of the C_{AROMATIC}-OH bond cleavage (dehydroxylation) of guaiacol molecule while methylcyclohexanediol formation involves the methyl group migration and the formation of two hydroxyl groups with the subsequent hydrogenation of the aromatic ring. [46-48] The formation of this diol molecule indicates that Ni₂P/MCM-22 has a limited dehydration capacity as a consequence of its lower acidity. This is in accordance with the low HDO efficiency exhibited at 220 °C. When temperature is increased to 260 °C, methylcyclohexanediol and anisole were also detected, yet with much lower selectivity (6.2 and 2.5 % respectively). In addition, a small amount of 1,1'-

bicyclohexyl is also observed, whose formation could occur in the larger 12-ring cavities characteristic of the **MWW** topology.

Regarding these results and literature data, a reaction scheme is proposed in Fig. 9. [48,49] Accordingly, under the experimental conditions employed, guaiacol can be transformed *via* three main reaction routes:

- 1) Guaiacol can be dehydroxylated leading to anisole, which can be further converted into various products. Firstly, anisole's aromatic ring can be completely hydrogenated leading to methoxycyclohexane, which can produce cyclohexane *via* demethoxylation. Secondly, anisole can undergo a demethylation and subsequent HDO yielding benzene, which can be consecutively hydrogenated to cyclohexene and cyclohexane.
- 2) Guaiacol can follow demethylation and dehydration reactions to produce phenol, which can be subsequently hydrogenated leading to cyclohexanone → cyclohexanol → cyclohexane.
- 3) Guaiacol can be converted into methylcyclohexanediol through methyl group migration and the formation of two hydroxyl groups with the subsequent hydrogenation of the aromatic ring. [46-48]

In addition, the cyclohexane formed through the mentioned processes can be converted into methylcyclopentane or hexane as a result of, respectively, isomerization or ring opening reactions. Finally, phenol can be alkylated with cyclohexene, formed as intermediate in the demethylation route, yielding to bicyclohexylphenol which, after subsequent hydrogenation and dehydration reactions, leads to 1,1-bicyclohexyl as final product.

This complex reaction pathway and product distribution is the result of the synergetic effect of Ni₂P nanoparticles with both metallic functionality, which promotes

hydrogenation reactions, and weak-moderate acidity 8 Lewis $\text{Ni}^{\delta+}$ sites and the Brønsted P–OH acid sites), with the strong acid sites provided by the zeolitic support. These acid sites with different strength catalyze dehydration, dehydroxylation, demethylation and demethoxylation as well as isomerization and alkylation reactions. In fact, in comparison with previous results reported in the literature, the strong acid sites of the zeolitic support favors the alcohols dehydration and are the main responsible of the cyclohexane isomerization and phenol alkylation reactions, leading to a further deoxygenation degree. [17,49] Therefore, catalytic results indicate that the HDO activity of the bifunctional catalysts mainly depends not only on hydrogenation capacity of Ni_2P but also on the acid properties of the final material. Likewise, the acid sites concentration seems to be associated with the BET area of the parent zeolite.

To confirm this relationship, the yield to complete deoxygenated compounds *versus* the surface density of acid sites, have been represented in Fig. 10, for both reaction temperatures. The surface density of acid sites has been roughly estimated, for each catalyst, as the ratio of the overall acidity values estimated from NH_3 -TPD analyses and the BET surfaces. Thus, the yields towards deoxygenated products, particularly at 260 °C, are higher for **MFI** samples, which exhibit larger surface density of acid sites. The deeper deoxygenation degree achieved over 2D ZSM-5 materials could be ascribed, firstly, to the better accessibility of the metallic nanoparticles, mainly allocated over the mesoporous and external surface of the zeolitic support, which favors their interaction with the organic substrate and, secondly, to the higher proportion and strength of the acid sites of different nature (Lewis $\text{Ni}^{\delta+}$ sites, P–OH moieties and acid sites from zeolitic support), which promotes alcohol dehydration, as well as isomerization and alkylation reactions, resulting in a higher yield of complete deoxygenated hydrocarbons.

4. Conclusions

Catalysts based on Ni₂P dispersed on 2D zeolites (L-ZSM-5, PI-ZSM-5 and MCM-22) have been synthesized and evaluated in guaiacol hydrodeoxygenation. All catalysts showed a high crystallinity degree after active phase incorporation; metal rich Ni₂P being the only phosphide phase detected. Textural properties of the loaded catalysts were reduced due to the pore blockage caused by the Ni₂P nanoparticles. For Ni₂P/MCM-22, this decrease mainly affected to the microporous system, whereas for the **MFI** zeolites, the decrease in the textural properties is more pronounced for the mesoporous system, suggesting that the Ni₂P nanoparticles are preferentially placed in the mesoporous channel and external surface of the support. In addition, Ni₂P incorporation produced an increase in the overall acidity, assigned to the generation of both new Lewis (Ni^{δ+} species) and Brønsted acid sites (P-OH groups), whose contribution seems to be higher for Ni₂P/ZSM-5 based catalysts. This fact, together with the higher accessibility of Ni₂P nanoparticles present over these supports, results in a higher guaiacol conversion values and HDO efficiencies. In fact, the material Ni₂P/PI-ZSM-5, in which these effects are more marked, exhibit the best catalytic results with a 78 % of conversion and 95 % of selectivity towards complete deoxygenated compounds, mainly, cyclohexane. In contrast, Ni₂P/MCM-22 presents lower HDO activity and a significant selectivity to oxygenated products.

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